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January 4th, 2026

Cosmology theory

Dark energy could be negative mass creating push but since something negative is always significantly weaker than a positive force like gravity i think the dark energy touching the gravity to push it gets consumed which means dark energy has to be regenerative to sustain the universe's natural balance.

I also believe the universe is a tesseract where the big bang is outwards and the big crunch is inward same with black holes not having a single center but also i think we could utilize multi point gravity to create planets with specific shapes and i believe quantum entanglement is one surface like a klein bottle rather than 2.